
AGRICULTURAL INNOVATION IS THE KEY TO DEVELOPMENT.

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Annotation.

The article reflects the work and innovation in the field of agriculture in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the years of independence.

Key words.

Agriculture, collective farm, state farm, irrigation, reclamation, farmer, saline lands, economy

Today, the leadership of Uzbekistan pays serious attention to the management and use of land and water resources. "You, the skilled masters of this field, know very well how difficult and hard it is to do farming in our region with limited water resources, to get abundant and high-quality harvest"⁷⁶, President Sh.M. Mirziyoev said at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the day of agricultural workers. Tasks such as further improvement of irrigation and melioration of irrigated lands, introduction of intensive methods in the field of agricultural production, first of all, modern agro-technologies that save water and resources have become an important issue. In order to solve these tasks, it is necessary to study the causes of the problems related to water management on a scientific basis and come to appropriate conclusions. In order to develop the national economy in our country, it was envisaged to improve modernization works not only in industry, but also in agriculture at the level of the current demand. In this regard, first of all, attention was paid to increasing soil fertility, improving the condition of irrigation facilities, providing them with modern technology and equipment, and improving the quality of livestock. According to the data, about 49% of the total irrigated land in our country has varying degrees of salinity, and almost 18% of it is strongly and moderately saline land. More than 23 percent of the irrigated lands belong to the category of poor quality lands. A large part of the lands with unsatisfactory

⁷⁶ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Ш.М.Мирзиёевнинг “Қишлоқ хўжалиги ходимлари куни”га бағишланган тантанали маросимдаги нутқи // “Халқ сўзи”, 2018, 22 май.

melioration status is the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, Bukhara, Jizzakh and Ferghana corresponds to the regions.

More than 55% of agricultural tractors and about 46% of tillage tractors have been used for more than 15 years, their power, productivity and fuel consumption levels do not meet modern requirements.

Our president deeply analyzed such negative situations and emphasized the need to eliminate existing shortcomings in a short time: "We need to look critically at many problems and issues in order to increase production productivity, speed up the efficiency of the work process and the achievement of final results. First of all, this is the land that feeds us. We need to increase its productivity. For this, we must first of all consider improvement of land reclamation and irrigation works as a priority goal. Secondly, providing agriculture with modern technology, techniques and equipment, and their production capabilities and quality should be satisfactory to farmers. If necessary, we need to provide them with machinery, fertilizer and other necessary equipment in a cheaper, preferential way"⁷⁷. State regulation of agrarian relations in the country and creation of an effective management system has become an urgent issue. It was not easy to increase the effectiveness of comprehensive reforms in agriculture, especially in the conditions of the market economy, as well as to eliminate existing imbalances in this field without the intervention of the state. The process of economic changes is largely related to solving the urgent task of forming the owners' stratum in the republic. In this regard, attention was paid to the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. "By ensuring the consistent development of small business and private entrepreneurship," said our first president I. Karimov, "we are achieving the formation of the middle class, which is the socio-political support and foundation of our society, and its strengthening. In order to further expand the scope of work in agriculture, state programs aimed at using modern irrigation systems and energy-saving technologies and increasing soil productivity were developed in this area.

In 2008-2012, within the framework of the State program for improving the reclamation of irrigated lands in our country, the total length of 10,530.2 kilometers of inter-farm and intra-farm collector-drainage networks was carried out for a total of more than 59 billion soums. In addition, in 586.6 kilometers of closed horizontal drainage networks in our country,

⁷⁷ Каримов И.А. Дехқончилик тараққиёти – фаровонлик манбаи.-Т.: "Ўзбекистон", 1994. 8 – бет.

As a result of restoration work on 9 reclamation pumping stations, 627 reclamation wells and a number of other reclamation facilities, the reclamation condition of 1 million hectares of irrigated land was improved, and the level of seepage water was reduced on an area of 300,000 hectares⁷⁸. As a result of the measures taken, since 2008, the reclamation condition of nearly 1,500,000 hectares of irrigated land in our country has improved, the areas with high groundwater have decreased by 415,000 hectares or about 10%, and the areas with strong and moderate salinity have decreased by 113,000 hectares⁷⁹.

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In 2003-2009, 21 projects with a value of 801.5 thousand US dollars were implemented in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan to improve the water supply and reclamation condition of the land, of which the foreign investment amounted to 560.4 thousand dollars. As a result of such comprehensive measures, the yield of agricultural crops has increased somewhat, and the possibility of increasing the income of farms has increased⁸⁰. Currently, investments are becoming an important factor of quality changes in the agricultural sector.

Thus, the technical and technological updates carried out in the agrarian sector networks, the modernization processes that are constantly being improved, played an important role in the development of the agricultural sector. Keeping abreast of scientific and technical innovations and using them effectively in production has become an urgent task of representatives of the agricultural sector.

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⁷⁹ Каримов И.А. 2014 йил юқори ўсиш суръатлари билан ривожланиш, барча мавжуд имкониятларни сафарбар этиш, ўзини оқлаган ислохотлар стратегиясини изчил давом эттириш йили бўлади. Ўзбекистон овози, 2014 йил, 18-январь.

⁸⁰ Сангиров Р. Мустақил Ўзбекистоннинг аграр сиёсати: ютуқлар ва муаммолар. –Тошкент: “MERIYUS” ХМНК, 2013. 44-бет.

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